

Mean yield performances of Padmanath. Assam, India, 1985-95.

Year	Location	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
		Padmanath	Negheribao	Amonabao
1985	Garumnuria	3.2	2.7	2.8
1986	Garumuria	3.0	-	2.7
	Korson	3.0	2.1	2.7
	Dhalpur	3.3	2.5	3.1
1987	Majuli	3.2	2.3	2.8
	Garumnuria	3.2	2.2	3.0
	Korson	3.1	2.1	2.6
1988	Dhalpur	3.3	2.4	2.9
	Jorhat	3.4	2.0	2.8
	Garumnuria	2.9	2.1	2.3
	Kalabari	3.1	-	-
	Dhalpur	2.5	1.6	1.1
	Dhemaji	3.2	-	-
1989	Dhakuakhana	3.4	-	-
	Jorhat	1.7	1.7	1.9
	Garumuria	3.1	1.8	2.2
	Dhemaji	3.0	-	-
1991	Dhakuakhana	3.2	-	-
	Garumuria	1.1	0.6	-
1992	Korson	3.1	1.4	1.7
	Garumuria	1.3	-	1.1
1994	Mahaijan	1.6	-	1.2
	Garumuria	3.7	-	2.7
1995	Garumuria	1.2	0.9	-
	Dolpota	2.0	1.8	-
	Dhakuakhana	2.1	1.2	-
	Ghilamora	3.0	1.5	-
Pooled av over years and locations		2.7	1.8	2.3

national check Jalamagna with 100% survival, stem elongation score 1, and yield of 2.1 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Padmanath is photoperiod-sensitive and flowers in late October. It is recommended for cultivation in flood-prone lowlands and deeply flooded regions of up to 2 m water in Assam. Padmanath exhibited moderate field tolerance for the major diseases and pests of deepwater rice. Good stem elongation up to 24.8 cm d⁻¹ was also recorded in rising floods. The variety also possesses excellent kneeing ability (38° average for all tillers).

Padmanath has medium-bold awned grains of the dimensions 7.4 × 3.1 mm and a test weight of 26.4 g for 1000 grains. The kernels are white and nonglutinous with a length-breadth ratio of 2.8. It is gaining popularity among the deepwater rice farmers of the state. ■

Panindra: a new deepwater rice for Assam, India

N. K. Sarma, B. N. Medhi, R. K. S. M. Baruah, M. J. B. K. Rao, D. K. Sarma, L. P. Upadhaya, H. Talukdar, R. Borgohain, M. K. Saikia, and H. N. Gogoi, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, North Lakhimpur, Assam 787001, India

Besides Padmanath, a new deepwater rice variety, we bred Panindra by the bulk pedigree method after hybridization between Pankaj and Negheribao. Pankaj is an improved high-yielding rice variety adapted to waterlogged situations and Negheribao is a local deepwater rice variety with excellent stem elongation capacity under rising floods up to 3-4 m.

The yield data of Panindra from 1988 to 1995 over 13 locations of the state are presented in the table. Panindra had a mean grain yield of 2.5 t ha⁻¹ over years and locations, exhibiting 33% superiority in yield than the local check variety Amonabao. Panindra was also found superior in grain yield by 50% than its deepwater parent Negheribao. Panindra is tall, elongating with medium slender grains, and suitable to grow in 1-2 m floods in Assam. The variety was also tested in the National Deepwater Rice Yield Trials (PVT6) under the name IET11875 from 1989 to 1993. During 1989, Panindra had a mean yield of 2.0 t ha⁻¹ as compared with the national check variety Jalamagna, which had the mean yield of 2.2 t ha⁻¹ across locations over India in PVT6.

Ranjini (MO 12): a high-yielding rice variety with blast and brown planthopper resistance

R. Devika, N. Remabai, A. Regina, and S. L. Kumari, Rice Research Station (RRS), Kerala Agricultural University, Moncompu, Thekkerala, P. O. Alappuzha, Kerala 688530, India

Mean paddy yield of Panindra. Assam, India, 1988-95.

Year	Location	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
		Panindra	Negheribao	Amonabao
1988	Garumuria	4.2	2.1	2.3
1990	Korson	4.1	2.9	-
1991	Garumuria	1.7	0.6	-
1992	Garumuria	1.9	-	1.1
	Mohaijan	2.9	-	1.2
1993	Garumuria	2.3	2.0	1.9
1994	Garumuria	3.1	-	2.7
	Dolpota	3.0	-	2.3
1995	Garumuria	1.1	0.9	-
	Dolpota	1.1	1.8	-
	Dhakuakhana	2.6	1.2	-
	Ghilamora	2.4	1.5	-
	Dhemaji	2.5	2.2	-
Pooled av		2.5	1.7	1.9

During 1990, Panindra had exhibited a mean yield of 2 t ha⁻¹ over India under IVT-DW; during 1992 it ranked second to Ghaghraghat (3.3 t ha⁻¹) and was superior to Jalamagna (1.8 t ha⁻¹).

Panindra is a photoperiod-sensitive variety, flowering by the last week of October in Assam. It is moderately tolerant of major diseases and pests but moderately susceptible to rice stem nematode, *Ditylenchus angustus*. It has outyielded the local deepwater rice varieties of Assam in plant and grain characters. Fair stem elongation rate (21 cm d⁻¹) was also observed for Panindra. Excellent kneeing ability (41°) of the tillers after the flood was also an added advantage to this variety.

Awnless grain of Panindra has a dimension of 7.8 × 2.6 mm with a test weight of 24.3 g for 1000 grains. The nonglutinous white kernel has a length-breadth ratio of 3.0. ■

Rice blast is one of the most serious diseases prevalent in Kuttanadu, the rice bowl of Kerala, a unique deltaic area, 0.5-2.0 m below MSL. Many popular high-yielding varieties of this locality lack blast resistance. A hybridization program was started at RRS, Moncompu, using locally accepted, high-yielding varieties, such as MO 5 and blast-resistant varieties such as

Table 1. Yield performance of Ranjini. Kerala, India.

Trial	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	Ranjini	Check ^a
RRS, Moncompu (1990-92) (3 seasons)	4.5	3.1
Multilocation trials (MLT) (6 research stations, 1991)	3.2	2.7
MLT (cultivators' fields in five locations, 1992)	5.6	3.2
All India Coordinated Trials (IVT-IME, 1993)	4.5	4.0
Farm trials in five locations	4.7	3.8

^aCheck variety was Asha at RRS, MLT, and farm trials; it was Retna for IVT-IME.

Table 2. Reaction of Ranjini to pests and diseases.^a RRS, Moncompu, Kerala, India.

Variety	Gall midge	BPH	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Blast
Ranjini	1.2	1.0	1.6	2.3	0.8
MO 5 (Asha)	3.2	1.6	3.0	3.1	5.0

^aScored by *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) on a scale of 0-9.

Improved Sona. The breeding line KAU M 28-1-1 (IET13706) from the cross MO 5/Improved Sona performed well in yield trials and was released as Ranjini (MO 12) in 1966 for use in the three seasons of Kerala (virippu, Apr-May to Aug-Sep; mundakan, Sep-Oct to Dec-Jan; and punja, Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr). It is a short-duration (115-120 d),

dwarf (90-95 cm) variety with red-kernel medium-bold grains, and resistant to blast and brown planthopper (BPH).

In yield trials, Ranjini consistently outyielded local checks (Table 1). It also showed tolerance for gall midge, sheath blight, and sheath rot (Table 2). ■

Seed technology

On-farm seed priming to accelerate germination in rainfed, dry-seeded rice

D. Harris, Centre for Arid Zone Studies, University of Wales, Bangor, Gwynedd, LL57 2UW, UK; and M. Jones, West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), Bouak, C te d'Ivoire

Demand for rice is increasing in West Africa, but farmers in upland rice areas face the twin constraints of drought and competition with weeds. Fast germination, establishment, and vigorous early growth of seedlings are essential to produce reasonable yields, particularly where presowing tillage and seedbed preparation are minimal.

Recent work at WARDA has produced interspecific hybrids by crossing *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* to give new plant types that offer high production potential allied to fast germination and enhanced weed suppression. Other work on improving the establishment of small-grained cereals, including rice in India, suggests that simple practices, such as soaking seed in water before sowing (on-farm seed priming), very effectively improve crop establishment. Combining fast-germinating varieties with on-farm seed priming should be of great benefit to rice

Time for 50% germination (h)

Effect of seed priming on germination. Numbers on columns are hours saved by priming.

farmers in marginal environments.

We tested 11 different varieties for their response to soaking in water for 24 h at 30 °C (see table). After soaking, the seeds were surface-dried with a cloth and then "sown" on moistened filter paper and kept at 30 °C. The figure compares the germination time for these primed seeds to nonprimed seeds. All lines responded positively to priming for 24 h, a limit previously determined as safe (i.e., not leading irreversibly to germination after surface drying) in Indian rice cultivars. The mean time for 50% germination of nonprimed seed was 46 h, which was reduced to 32 h by priming. The time saved by priming ranged from 7 h in CG20, an *O. glaberrima* variety, to 20 h in

Names and plant types of varieties in the figure.

Number in figure	Variety	Type
1	WAB 56-50	Improved <i>O. sativa</i>
2	WAB 56-104	Improved <i>O. sativa</i>
3	WABC 165	Improved <i>O. sativa</i>
4	CG 14	<i>O. glaberrima</i>
5	CG 20	<i>O. glaberrima</i>
6	WAB 450-24-3-2-P18-HB	<i>O. sativa/O. glaberrima</i>
7	WAB 450-1-B-P-106-HB	<i>O. sativa/O. glaberrima</i>
8	WAB 450-24-2-3-P33-HB	<i>O. sativa/O. glaberrima</i>
9	LAC 23	Traditional <i>O. sativa</i>
10	Moroberekan	Traditional <i>O. sativa</i>
11	SP 4	Traditional <i>O. sativa</i>

SP4, a traditional *O. sativa* variety.

Participatory research using on-farm seed priming in India has shown that farmers prefer to soak their seeds for less than 24 h to avoid the possibility of premature germination if sowing is delayed for any reason. They report a range of benefits following overnight soaking, and our preliminary tests of germination following priming for 8 and 16 h support this conclusion. Further research is in progress to quantify the benefits of seed priming under West African conditions. ■

Comments. If you have comments or suggestions about the IRRN, please write to the editor.